

Emotion estimation from video footage with LSTM

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Abstract

Emotion estimation is a field that has been studied for a long time, and several approaches using machine learning models exist. In this paper, we present an LSTM model that utilizes Blendshapes produced by the MediaPipe library to analyse facial expressions detected from a live-streamed camera feed. This model is trained on the FER2013 dataset and achieves an accuracy of 71% accuracy and an F1-score of 62%, which meets the accuracy benchmark of the FER2013 dataset, while significantly reducing computational cost. For the sake of reproducibility, the code repository, datasets, and models proposed in this paper, in addition to the pre-print, can be found on Hugging Face at: <https://huggingface.co/papers/2501.13432>

Keywords: Emotion estimation, Computer vision, Social robotics, Neural networks, Blendshapes

JEL Classification: D8 , H51

MSC Classification: 35A01 , 65L10 , 65L12 , 65L20 , 65L70

1 Introduction

In social robotics, many parts of a robot system are integrated into a single system. Typically, the more complex the system is, the better it will be at performing tasks, which are more commonly focused on elderly care or patient care. In addition to skeletal and motion structures, the subsystems of a robot include interaction modules and sensory functions, such as speech, vision, and hearing. Since human emotion is a

large part of any interaction between two or more humans, it is important for robots to interpret human emotion through sensory inputs, such as speech, voice tone, facial expressions, body poses, and hand gestures, gaze direction, and head orientation. In this work, we focus solely on emotion estimation from facial expressions due to its importance [1].

Emotion estimation from facial expressions, more commonly referred to as facial emotion recognition (FER), generally involves three steps: 1) face detection: identify a face in a camera stream or image and localizing its boundaries; 2) feature extraction: identify and extract most relevant information from the previously detected face, many approaches exist, more popular is by setting key points as a vector for the most relevant parts of the face, such as the tip of the nose and the ends of the mouth in two-dimensional or three-dimensional coordinates; and 3) expression classification: using extracted features as inputs for a classification model that predicts the emotion conveyed by the facial expression.

The proposed emotion estimation system functions as a feedback mechanism that helps drive a conversation or an interaction between a human and a robot. The system enables a robot to detect real-time human reactions through their facial expression and potentially change the topic or the approach of a conversation or an action.

The scope of this research was limited by the availability of data and computational resources. Consequently, emotion classification was restricted to three classes instead of the original seven proposed previously (Happy, Sad, Angry, Afraid, Surprise, Disgust, and Neutral) [2]. These three classes with labels (happy, sad), while all other emotions were grouped into a general category under an undefined label (Unknown).

The system development process begins with a full data processing pipeline, which includes loading, cleaning, augmenting, extracting features, and visualizing data. Then, the data are input into the model for training. During inference, the trained model is integrated into the Gaze Project¹, where it facilitates facial detection/localization and feature extraction. Then, the trained model classifies facial expressions on the basis of the features.

Some considerations should be noted. First, the FER2013 [3] dataset is categorized as a challenge dataset, i.e., it is not built and optimized for research purposes. It contains a group of non-relevant images, such as animations and covered faces, which do not provide useful information to the model. Additionally, model training and testing are performed on a laptop equipped with a NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3050 Mobile GPU.

This study serves as a proof of concept (POC) for a research paper that will be discussed in the future work section, which is a later part of this paper. In the context of emotion estimation for embedded systems in social robotics, the main contributions of this study are as follows:

1. Building a compact and cost-effective model that fits for inference on a microcomputer, while considering the spatial and temporal aspects of facial expression.
2. Using the MediaPipe library Face Landmarker task, which is for face localization and feature extraction, and incorporating Blendshapes [4] as features, a technique rarely employed in FER applications.

¹https://gitlab.com/Hoog-V/gaze/-/tree/main/gaze_estimator_python_rpi?ref_type=heads

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 covers related work, Section 3 details the methods, Section 4 discusses the ablation studies, Section 5 presents the results, Section 6 discusses the results and findings of the study, Section 7 concludes the study, Section 8 presents the future work to be based on this study.

2 Related Work

Facial emotion recognition has been an active research area for a long time [2]. The main challenges for building an emotion estimation system are [5]:

- The complexity of the emotion patterns.
- The emotions are time-varying.
- The process is user and context dependent.

Many methods exist for facial detection and tracking, such as the Haar cascade algorithm, and other methods for feature extraction, such as the classical algorithms Histogram Oriented Gradient (HOG), and Scale Invariant Feature Transform (SIFT) [6] [7], or, more recently, the Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) [8] and transformer encoders [9] have been employed to detect faces and extract features. Classification models also employ CNNs, Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN)s or hybrid architectures [8] [10].

2.1 Feature extraction

Feature extraction can be considered a special type of data dimensionality reduction aimed at identifying a subset of informative variables from image data [11]. The most common approach for extracting quality features from images of faces involves estimating landmarks [12] [13] [14] on the face. One approach involves identifying the tip of the nose and then segmenting it by cropping the sphere centered at this tip. Then, the eyebrows, mouth corners, eye corners and possibly many other facial landmarks are identified on the segmented sphere. Finally, by measuring the distances between landmarks [15] and changes in their positions, facial expression can be interpreted [16].

2.1.1 History

Looking back on the evolution of FER, one of the methods used to extract features is the HOG [6], which determines edge presence, direction, and magnitude. Another method is SIFT [7], which follows a four-step process: 1) constructing the scale space, 2) localizing crucial points 3) assigning orientation, and 4) assigning unique fingerprints. A feature extraction method that still often used nowadays is Support Vector Machine (SVM) [17] [10].

More recently, feature extraction has been performed using deep neural networks [8] [10], such as fully connected networks (FCNs) or CNNs, which construct models consisting of a number of layers and hyperparameters. The complexity of the data and the required performance quality, in addition to the available computational resources, influence which model is implemented.

Fig. 1 Image annotated with MediaPipe

2.1.2 MediaPipe

In this work, we used the MediaPipe [4] [18] library for facial recognition, tracking, feature extraction, and landmark detection. Using the Face Landmarker task could have three outputs for each image or frame, these are 468 3D landmark vectors, 52 Blendshapes, and facial transformation matrices. In previous works [19], two approaches were proposed for feature extraction, one of which involved used MediaPipe to extract features from images. The results indicated that using this library can be more effective than using deep learning networks such as CNNs. In the case of subtle facial expressions, the more intense facial expressions are, the smaller the performance gap between the two approaches. In the most intense case, CNNs yield better results for most emotions.

In [?] presented FaceLocalizationNet which performs simultaneous face detection and landmark localization, and the network used for the localization is RetinaFace [20].

In another study [21], MediaPipe was compared to OpenFace for landmark detection. OpenFace [22] uses OpenCV to detects 68 facial landmarks, whereas MediaPipe uses TensorFlow [23] to detect 468 landmarks that are arranged in fixed quads and represented by their coordinates (x, y, z) . Figure 1 shows an image annotated with the landmarks used for facial expression recognition.

Another work is [24], which suggests adding a CNN model to process the MediaPipe library 3D landmark vectors and improve the landmark placement precision, working on 2D facial photographs.

2.1.3 Blendshapes

The second output of the MediaPipe face landmark detection task model consists of Blendshapes, which provide an approximate semantic parameterization and a simple linear model for facial expressions [25]. This technique originated in the industry before gaining traction in academia and has been widely used in computer graphics. Although the Blendshapes technique is conceptually simple, developing a full Blendshapes face model is computationally intensive. To express a complete range of realistic expressions, one face might require more than 600 Blendshapes.

Fig. 2 Histogram for the Blendshapes of the image in Figure 1 via MediaPipe

The construction of a single Blendshapes model was originally guided by the facial action coding system (FACS) [26]. This system enables the manual coding of all facial displays, which are referred to as action units, and more than 7000 combinations have been observed. The FACS action units are the smallest visibly discriminable changes in a facial display, and combinations of FACS action units can be used to describe emotional expressions [27] and global distinctions between positive and negative expressions.¹

MediaPipe incorporates ARKit face Blendshapes², which consists of 52 Blendshapes that describe the face parts and expressions. These are quantified with probability scores in the range (0–1), indicating the presence of specific Blendshapes, as shown in Figure 1, while Figure 2 present a Blendshapes histogram.

2.2 Emotion classification

For emotion classification, many approaches have been used in research, such as support vector machines (SVM) [7], which have been implemented with linear as well as radial basis functions, and stochastic gradient descent (SGD) classifiers, which achieved approximately 95% accuracy on the Radboud Faces Database

¹<https://medium.com/@samiratra95/blendshapes-a-facial-expressions-representation-6352ecd99009>

²<https://arkit-face-blendshapes.com/>

(RaFD) [28]. [19] presented a comparison between two approaches, namely, a MediaPipe-SVM and a CNN-LSTM. MediaPipe and the CNN were employed for feature extraction and the SVM and LSTM [29] were used for classification. Experiments have shown that features extracted using MediaPipe are superior to those extracted by the CNN. Consequently, the classification performance of the first combination is better than that of the second approach.

One approach in [30] used ResNet [31] blocks in addition to the Squeeze-and-excitation network [32] for expression classification, shows the improvements that can be achieved using the correct transfer learning approach, also used the model suggested to examine the important features and where the major information of the face is located using feature maps, which will be further discussed in section 6.

Another type of image classification method adopts CNNs. [6] used a sequential model of three convolutional layers and a dense layer to classify input features and achieved high accuracy on the dataset used.

Since the model being developed is designed for video processing, where data are sequential, as stated in [33], the choice of an appropriate RNN is crucial. Just as a CNN is a neural network that is specialized for processing a grid of values such as an image, a RNN is a neural network that is specialized for processing a sequence of values or sequential data.

When working with sequential data, such as videos, and considering temporal dependencies between images, a RNN is the best choice [8]. The use of an LSTM, which is a special type of RNN, aims to address the vanishing gradient and exploding gradient problems that are common in RNN training; [34] compared the results, the network including a CNN part and an RNN part delivers better accuracy than a network with CNN layers only and that is approximately 20% higher in accuracy.

Another work discussing RNNs is [10], where a CNN-LSTM architecture was suggested as a facial recognition system that could understand the spatiotemporal properties in a video.

3 Methods

In this section, we discuss our approach to building the emotion estimation system, starting with the dataset used and the data processing techniques, then building and optimizing the model, and finally, we evaluate and test the performance of the model.

3.1 Dataset

Since the model being developed is intended for video-based inference, selecting a video dataset with different facial expressions was the first priority. [8] found a group of datasets, some of which include videos, such as MMI[35][36] and AFEW7.0[37]. However, due to computational constraints and the intensive data preprocessing required for video-based datasets, we opted to use an image-based dataset instead.

Among the datasets that were considered, MultiPIE [38] was considered because of its image quality and size. We also considered the Radboud Faces Database RaFD [28] for the structure of the database and the quality of the distribution. Another choice

was AffectNet [39], owing to its suitable size and popularity as a benchmark to evaluate the performance of models in many studies and experiments.

In this work, we used the FER2013 dataset [3], which was chosen for its simplicity. This dataset contains a sufficient number of 48x48 grayscale images that are easy to obtain through this open-access dataset.

The dataset was downloaded from Kaggle³ in .csv format. The data includes the class, image pixel array grayscale values, and the data split as columns and training examples as rows.

The FER2013 dataset [3] is categorized into 7 classes: happy, sad, angry, afraid, surprise, disgust, and neutral. The full dataset is split into three groups, training, public testing, and private testing, which are used as the training set, validation set and test set, respectively. The distribution of images across these subsets is shown in Table 1:

Class - Split	Full	Training	Public test	Private test
Happy	8989	7215	895	879
Sad	6077	4830	653	594
Angry	4953	3995	467	491
Afraid	5121	4097	496	528
Surprise	4002	3171	415	416
Disgust	547	436	56	55
Neutral	6198	4965	607	626

Table 1 FER2013 dataset: classes and splits

The table shows that 1) the happy, sad, and neutral classes have the highest number of samples, whereas the disgust class has the lowest representation, and 2) the public test and private test splits are well-suited for use as the validation set and test set, respectively. In the next subsections, the data processing techniques applied to restructure the database in a form that best serves the requirements of the model being built are discussed.

3.2 Data processing and cleaning

Since the FER2013 dataset [3] was originally designed as a challenge dataset, additional data processing steps are required to adapt it for research and real-world robotic applications. To ensure its suitability for emotion estimation in this context, a series of data cleaning and preprocessing steps must be applied.

3.2.1 Creating training data classes

The first step in data processing involves splitting the dataset into three subsets: the training, validation, and test sets. Owing to class imbalance, we decided not to use the full set of available training class images; instead, we included a portion of the available samples, as shown in Table 2:

³<https://www.kaggle.com/c/challenges-in-representation-learning-facial-expression-recognition-challenge/data>

Class	Happy	Sad	Angry	Afraid	Surprise	Disgust	Neutral
Count	4000	4000	1500	1500	1500	Maximum possible	1500

Table 2 Training set classes counts

These values were chosen on the basis of the model’s focus on classifying happy, sad, and unknown classes only, instead of the full 7 emotions in the dataset. Assigning 4000 samples to the main emotion classes ensures a more balanced dataset. Most other classes are allocated 1500 samples, keeping their combined total at 6000, in addition to the approximately 400 images for the disgust class. This distribution provides a sufficient number of training examples while ensuring that the unknown class remains aligned with happy and sad emotions.

Table 1 shows that including more training examples from each class is possible for some classes, but including all examples could lead to an imbalanced data representation and a lower-quality distribution.

3.2.2 Readability by MediaPipe

To clean the dataset and avoid runtime errors caused by images that MediaPipe cannot detect, a detection program was developed. All the images in the training set were processed through MediaPipe, and the undetectable images in the dataset were excluded.

This process resulted in the following numbers for each class, as shown in Table 3.

Class	Happy	Sad	Angry	Afraid	Surprise	Disgust	Neutral
Counts	377	835	597	616	239	72	261

Table 3 Number of images MediaPipe could not detect

As described earlier, MediaPipe detects the main parts of the face and estimates landmark vectors and blendshapes for each image. If a part of the face is obstructed, this process becomes infeasible. Images with occlusions, such as those in Figure 3, are considered undetectable.

3.2.3 Indexing the test set

This step resulted in an unexplainable high error rate in model performance. As a tracking method, a column was added to the test set in the CSV file, which assigns a number to each image in the FER2013 dataset. This number remains associated with the image through all the steps of data processing and is transferred to the Blendshapes of the image when the Blendshapes dataset [40] is created.

This step helps to track images with high error rates when the model is evaluated using the test set, facilitating the visualization of the images or creating different types of plots to check for patterns in the images causing the errors.

Fig. 3 Images undetectable by MediaPipe

3.2.4 Augmenting the training set

To increase the number of training images and the variety of poses and, as a result, improve the generalizability of the model, data augmentation was applied. By generating new examples [41] with random transformations, the model’s generalizability was enhanced. The augmentation techniques that were used are as follows:

1. Random horizontal slip.
2. Random rotation of 0.2×180 degrees in the clockwise direction and counterclockwise direction.

These techniques are based on the use case of the model. Since it is designed for a social robot, horizontal flipping will enable the robot to interpret reflections and provide a valid facial image but with a different camera angle. Additionally, random rotations improve model performance by accounting for natural head tilts and rotations, which commonly occur in human interactions. For a robot, the ability to detect and classify facial expressions from various angles is crucial for real-world applications.

Processing the image dataset through the augmentation process results in a new extended dataset with more than 20000 images across the three classes described earlier.

3.2.5 Blendshapes dataset

Using MediaPipe to detect faces in a video stream requires extensive processing of the data before they are input into the classification model. To integrate the model with a face detection program, the model needs to be trained to interpret the same output from the program. Consequently, the full dataset is converted into a Blendshapes dataset [40], which is used to train the model.

Using the Blendshapes was preferred to the 3D Landmark vectors to save a significant amount of computation at the inference stage, and that is because using the 3D Landmarks vectors is equivalent to using 1404 features for representing the image, while using the Blendshapes equals having 52 features only.

3.3 Model architecture and training

The classification model is primarily built using LSTM layers [29], with the exception of the last dense layer employing softmax activation to produce classification scores from the last layer’s output.

The decision to incorporate LSTM layers to build the model was made for the following reasons:

1. The model is designed to be integrated into a video stream and to classify faces, which means that it operates on a time-series basis, where each input depends on the sequence of preceding inputs. Given this dependency, using one type of recurrent neural network (RNN) [33] is intuitive, as it retains information from past states in addition to the current input.
2. Another reason for this choice is that LSTM is a type of gated recurrent unit (GRU) [42]. One of its advantages is the presence of an internal gating mechanism that helps filter out nonrelevant features, allowing the model to focus only on the most critical features.
3. LSTM stands for long short-term memory. A key advantage of this network over the other types of recurrent neural networks is its ability to maintain long-term dependencies well, not only short-term dependencies, as is the case with RNN [43] and GRU networks.

Once the LSTM layer was selected, the next step was designing the model architecture. Several key factors were considered, such as accuracy, recall, precision, latency, and model size. After a few experiments to determine the best parameters, the Keras tuner [44] was employed as an architecture search framework to determine the best values for the hyperparameters. The search space was defined on the basis of prior experiments and empirical intuition⁴.

The final model was trained for 5000 epochs, which required approximately two days to finish. The batch size was 128, and the architecture was with the keras utils function and as shown in Figure 4. The optimizer used for training was AdamW [45] [46], with a learning rate of 1.09e-06, a global clipping norm of 1, and AMSGrad [47]. The adopted callbacks were the checkpoint callback and early-stopping callback.

Fig. 4 Model structure

For the loss function, categorical cross-entropy was used to encode the labels of the images as one-hot vectors, and the metrics for evaluation were loss, categorical cross-entropy, categorical accuracy, and the F1-score.

⁴<https://medium.com/p/1833f774051f>

3.4 Model evaluation

The model evaluation process is conducted for every set of weights produced by the checkpoint callback and shows improved training and validation performance metrics. Approximately every 100 epochs, a model weights set is saved.

Each model is evaluated by predicting the labels of the test dataset images' blendshapes, and comparing them to the ground truth labels. A loss, categorical cross-entropy, categorical accuracy, and F1-score are calculated for the model, and take F1-score as the main metric to optimize for.

4 Ablation Studies

To gain a better understanding of the model and its potential applications, we conducted several ablation studies. These studies aimed to determine the best number of Blendshapes, the most effective type of model, and the best loss function.

4.1 Selection of relevant Blendshapes

To improve the efficiency of the model, lower the computational requirements, and output quality classification results with less processing time and memory usage, a set of Blendshapes returned from MediaPipe is required. Since the model processes detected faces in each video frame, a total of 52 Blendshapes, based on the ARKit face Blendshapes, is required.

This approach was developed after observing, as might be obvious in Figure 2, that some of the Blendshapes do not have a score. We tested the whole dataset [40] and found that some of the Blendshapes do not have scores across all images.

We considered two strategies: 1) count the number of times a certain Blendshape has a zero score and discard it if it has a high count, and 2) set a threshold value and count how many times each of the Blendshapes have a score that exceeds this threshold.

After testing various values for the high-count threshold in the first approach and different thresholds values in the second approach, 0.4 was selected as the threshold, and 100 was set as a high-count number. Thus, for any Blendshape, if its score does not exceed 0.4 in more than 100 images in the dataset [40], it is discarded.

This choice was made for the following reasons:

- Counting zero values and making decisions on the basis of these criteria would have resulted in a small and nonrelevant number of Blendshapes being discarded, which would not have improved the efficiency of the model.
- Using the second approach and setting a threshold higher than 0.4 would have resulted in discarding Blendshapes with a wide range of probabilities. These Blendshapes contribute valuable information to the model during training, and removing them would result in a more compact model but reduced accuracy and performance.
- Setting a count higher than 100 would have resulted in a significant decrease in the number of Blendshapes being used, which would make it more difficult for the model to learn.

These reasons were validated through experimentation, i.e., training models on different data collections, testing their performance and size, and then making decisions for every number mentioned.

This process resulted in the use of 27 of 52 Blendshapes listed as important in Appendix A, reducing the size of the model while keeping the performance metrics, such as the accuracy and F1-score the same.

For further clarification, Figure 5 shows the scatter plot for the 52 Blendshapes, highlighting how many of them exhibit low values. This finding suggests that certain Blendshape contribute minimal information and can be omitted.

Fig. 5 Blendshape scatter plot for a sample image

4.2 Dense neural network model

To construct a faster model with shorter prediction time (latency) than that of the LSTM network, another network that is less complex was built, and a fully connected (dense) layer was chosen as the only layer in the whole model. After a few optimization experiments, the model achieved high performance. However, when it was integrated into a real-time system using a camera stream, it lacked acceptable stability and kept oscillating between the classes without any change in the view of the camera, leading to predictions with insufficient accuracy.

4.3 CCE and MSE loss functions

In earlier stages of research, the mean squared error [48] loss function was used for training the LSTM model. However, because the MSE function calculates the distance between the prediction and the ground truth—instead of calculating the probability difference—it is more suited for regression applications. Thus, the loss function had to be changed after a certain point.

$$MSE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 \quad (1)$$

In contrast to the cross-entropy, categorical cross-entropy measures the difference between the predicted probability of the correct category and the ground-truth label, making it more suitable for classification tasks. Given that the application involves three classes, categorical cross-entropy was chosen.

$$CCE = - \sum_{i=1}^N y_i \log(\hat{y}_i) \quad (2)$$

For potential improvements, categorical focal cross-entropy [49] was considered to address class imbalance in the dataset. Although it was originally designed for object detection, experiments have shown that categorical focal cross-entropy enhances classification model results.

$$FL = -\alpha(1 - \hat{y})^\gamma CCE(y, \hat{y}) \quad (3)$$

5 Results

The results obtained from the model were close to the classification benchmark of the dataset⁵ comparing to models with no extra training data and being a non-transformer neural network. such as the models mentioned in Table 4

Model name	Accuracy
LocalLearning BOW [3]	67.48%
DeepEmotion [50]	70.02%
Ours	71.99%
Ad-Corre [51]	72.03%
VGGNet [52]	73.28%
ResNet18 With Tricks [53]	73.70%

Table 4 Benchmark Models

The best results obtained from the model on the test set were as follows:

- Loss = 0.6238
- Categorical cross-entropy = 0.6235
- Categorical accuracy = 0.7199

⁵<https://paperswithcode.com/sota/facial-expression-recognition-on-fer2013>

- F1-score = 0.6298

The confusion matrix for the model is shown in Table 5.

Ground truth	Predicted			
	Class	0	1	2
	0	251	35	5
	1	110	850	150
	2	21	140	84

Shows the classes as 0: happy, 1: unknown, and 2: sad.

Table 5 Confusion matrix

Experimenting with different architectures, hyperparameters, and longer training times did not yield improved results.

However, the confusion matrix continued to fluctuate, showing inconsistent classification improvements for the happy and sad classes. At one point, the classification of sad improved, while at another, the happy class was favoured, revealing a bias toward the happy class. To assign weights to each class, the model focused on the happy and sad classes, assigning them greater importance while allocating less weight to the unknown class, which is easily classified in all the experiments. However, some limitations prevent experiments with class weights.

When the model was integrated into the test camera stream, as demonstrated in the demo video⁶, the model outputs classifications for happy and sad. However, when facial features change, the unknown class is frequently assigned. For all other facial expressions, the unknown class remains the predicted output.

6 Discussion

Considering the use case the model is being developed for, makes it necessary to optimize for the latency and model size in addition to the compiler metrics, such as the loss, cross-entropy, accuracy, and F1-score, since they are critical in the implementation step of the model on an edge device to be used for inference in real time.

Regarding the model size, Models in [3], [9], [15], [30], [54], [51], [55], [53], [52], [50] are of large size which makes them unfit for implementation on an edge device, yet some of them might show better performance metrics. while in [56], a model of CNN-BiLSTM is presented, which makes the LSTM part of it similar to ours in processing the temporal dimension of the data but without using Bidirectional layers, and that is because part of the experiments in 3.3 showed that it does not improve the results only increase the time required for training. while the first part, which is a CNN, is much different from MediaPipe, although both of them are concerned with the spatial dimension of the data, and from 2.1.2 in [19], MediaPipe shows superior results to a CNN model for feature extraction.

In 4.1 suggested and validated an approach to decrease the number of Blendshapes included in representing the face, and used a statistical approach to choose the best

⁶<https://youtu.be/RdcjA9ScBmI>

Blendshapes to use, and it showed the Blendshapes to be included are a majority from the brows, eyes, and mouth and as shown in appendix A while in [30] generates feature maps show that the mouth and the nose are the parts with most information and importance for classification, and this difference might be resulting from the difference in the datasets, and the approach used, since Blendshapes are a different concept from the feature maps suggested. also notice that only two Blendshapes of the 52 in the ARKit set are representing the nose, which might be hiding some information.

7 Conclusion

We focused on building a model to be implemented on a microcomputer in a social robot to detect faces in a camera video stream, extract Blendshapes as features from the face, and classify facial expressions on the basis of the emotion that they represents whether it is happiness, sadness or unknown.

We demonstrated that a 4-layer LSTM model is a suitable architecture to classify the Blendshapes of faces in camera stream frames. The model exhibited good stability with respect to time. Note that good results were obtained from the video stream even after the model was trained on an image dataset. In addition, the model achieves results comparable to the benchmark dataset with no loss in accuracy through the pipeline of feature extraction and classification. This approach saves considerable memory and computation in comparison to those of other available methods.

Besides all of that, conducted ablation studies and suggested methods for further improving the resource efficiency of the model and performance.

8 Future work

Based on this research, a new model will be built and trained on the Aff-Wild2 Dataset [57] [58] [59] [60] [61] [62] [63] [64] [65] [66] [5] and tested on other datasets in addition to Aff-Wild2, to deliver results on facial expression classification, action units, and valence/arousal. and will be using techniques implemented and discussed in this research paper. Afterward, we could work on another research that includes other modalities such as voice tone, body pose, and natural language to estimate emotions. and using compound facial expressions [67] to have a more accurate and detailed estimation for human emotion.

Further studies about reducing the feature count will be conducted on other types of data and features.

Declarations

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Conflict of interest

The author declares that he has no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The dataset used to train the model reported in the paper can be found at the following link: <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/sameratrah/fer2013-blendshapes-dataset-example-partial>

Code availability

The code repository where the research was performed can be found at this link: https://github.com/Samir-atra/Emotion_estimation_from_video_footage_with_LSTM_ML_algorithm

Authors' contributions

Not applicable

Abbreviations

- **LSTM**: Long-Short Term Memory.
- **FER**: Facial Emotion Recognition.
- **POC**: Proof Of Concept.
- **HOG**: Histogram Oriented Gradients.
- **SIFT**: Scale Invariant Feature Transform.
- **CNN**: Convolutional Neural Network.
- **RNN**: Recurrent Neural Network.
- **FCN**: Fully Connected Network.
- **FACS**: Facial Action Coding System.
- **SVM**: Support Vector Machine.
- **SGD**: Stochastic Gradient Descent.
- **RaFD**: Radboud Faces Database.
- **GRU**: Gated Recurrent Unit.
- **MSE**: Mean Squared Error.
- **CCE**: Categorical Cross Entropy.
- **FL**: Focal Loss.

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Appendix A Important Blendshapes

Index	Name	Importance
0	Neutral	No
1	Brow down left	Yes
2	Brow down right	Yes
3	Brow inner up	Yes
4	Brow outer up left	Yes
5	Brow outer up right	Yes
6	Cheek puff	No
7	Cheek squint left	No
8	Cheek squint right	No
9	Eye blink left	Yes
10	Eye blink right	Yes
11	Eye look down left	Yes
12	Eye look down right	Yes
13	Eye look in left	Yes
14	Eye look in right	Yes
15	Eye look out left	Yes
16	Eye look out right	Yes
17	Eye look up left	Yes
18	Eye look up right	Yes
19	Eye squint left	Yes
20	Eye squint right	Yes
21	Eye wide left	No
22	Eye wide right	No
23	Jaw forward	No
24	Jaw left	No
25	Jaw open	Yes
26	Jaw right	No
27	Mouth close	No
28	Mouth dimple left	No
29	Mouth dimple right	No
30	Mouth frown left	No
31	Mouth frown right	No
32	mouth funnel	No
33	Mouth right	No
34	Mouth lower down left	Yes
35	Mouth lower down right	Yes
36	Mouth press left	No
37	Mouth press right	No
38	Mouth pucker	Yes
39	Mouth right	No
40	Mouth roll lower	No
41	Mouth roll upper	No
42	Mouth shrug lower	No
43	Mouth shrug upper	No
44	Mouth smile left	Yes
45	Mouth smile right	Yes
46	Mouth stretch left	Yes
47	Mouth stretch right	Yes
48	Mouth upper up left	Yes
49	Mouth upper up right	Yes
50	Nose sneer left	No
51	Nose sneer right	No

Table A1 Important Blendshapes for FER2013 dataset according to the criteria in the first ablation study